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Profanity of Witch Hunting in Rajasthan: An Overview through Historical and Sociological Lens

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INTRODUCTION

If you are thinking that witch hunting is a phenomenon that dates back to primitive society practices, you need to rethink. As per recorded data, in India still hundreds of women are murdered in the name of witch hunting every year and the number will rise if we add the unrecorded data. In India we are on verge of digitisation, we are launching missiles in fraction of seconds, but the picture of another side is much more darker and shivering where hundreds of women are brutally murdered in name of witch hunting.

Who are witches? When we talk about science there is no such term in the dictionary but the term is well placed in the dictionary of superstition. “Witchcraft” does it really occur? Yes, if we believe that mishap happens if a cat crosses the road, then definitely witchcraft happens too. If not, then witchcraft has no existence. Lots of researches are done to find out the reasons behind witch hunting and the fact comes out is “witch hunting is a form of violence against women, just like rape, it has nothing to do with the practice of witchcraft”. We will discuss the reasons of witch hunting in details later in the paper.

Let’s have a look on the practice of Witch Hunting with special reference to India. The classical period of witch hunting dates back to the 14th century when certain people were labelled as 'witches' and executed across Europe, Africa and Asia. The victims included Joan of

Arc who was burnt alive at the tender age of 19 at the stake for heresy on May 30, 1431.[Ryan Shaffer, 2014]

In India, witch hunting dates back hundreds of years. It emanated in the tribal society and villages of Rajasthan which is now infamously known as the 'Kaala Jadu Ka Gadh'. Witch hunting is being practiced in the State and has become a burning issue, where predominantly women fall prey to this heinous crime.

Witch hunting involves the branding of victims, women as witches, either after an observation made by an 'ojha' or 'bej', a witch doctor. The victim who is branded as a witch is subjected to numerous forms of torture, beatings, burns, paraded naked through the village, forced to eat human excrement and sometimes even raped. In most of the cases their hair is cut off and the victim and their children are socially ostracised and even put to death.

The practice of witch hunting is purely connected to the prevalence of patriarchal attitudes and an opposition to women's rights over property. The death of a child, a disease outbreak in a village, bad weather, a meagre harvest. These are some of the reasons why women in India are accused of sorcery, branded as witches, and hunted. Public health and development failures thus become exacerbated by forces of patriarchy, misogyny, and the caste system. Some states have outlawed witch hunts, but the practice continues with thousands of women hunted each year; hundreds are tortured and murdered. Lack of education and superstitious beliefs have contributed to the continuation of this antiquated practice of witch hunting in India.

International Peer Review Multidisciplinary Journal

RATIONALE: Why we are talking about witch hunting in 21st century? Simply, because the practice of witch-hunting in India, which includes extreme violence and deep rooted beliefs have led to the torture and murder of alleged witches. State Governments and rationalists have been trying to address the issue but have failed on several counts.

The data are here to prove the statement:

The National Crime Records Bureau says 2,097 murders were committed between 2000 and 2012 where witch hunting was the motive. [Crime in India 2012 Statistics]

According to the Times of India, a National Crime Records Bureau report revealed that more than 1,700 women were murdered for witchcraft between 1991 and 2010. The numbers are

undoubtedly actually higher, as many cases go unreported or authorities refuse to register the cases.[TOI, 2012-12-2]

Why we choose Rajasthan?

On 30th October, 2017 a news report was published in Hindustan Times entitled as “ 127 witch-hunting cases in Rajasthan in last 2 years, activists slam police”.It’s not the only news report, there are many news reports encountered every year, every month, which shouts about the evil practice of witch hunting in Rajasthan.

Even the actual numbers are much higher than what recorded. The activist Tara Ahluwalia, chairperson of the Bhilwara-based Bal Evam Mahila Chetna Samiti said that he actual number of cases, in which women have been killed or ostracised from their community after being branded as a witch, are much higher than what the government records indicate. She adds “Many a time, when a woman goes to a police station to report about such an incident, the police refuse to register cases under the witch hunting act. The police dilly-dally often results in many such cases going unreported.” [Hindustan Times, 2017-10-03]

So, what next?

As researchers and academicians, we choose this topic to unearth the reasons of the social evil: Witch hunting in Rajasthan.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the paper are enlisted below:

- i. To draw a historical overview of witch hunting practice in India.
- ii. To explore the relevant reasons that gives impetus to witch hunting in Rajasthan.
- iii. To analyse the role of government in eradication process and causes of its failure.

METHODOLOGY

The present study was done by the method of qualitative summative secondary data analysis. The data were extracted for specific variables of interest, including newspaper report, television news report, books, articles and NGOs’ report, of last 15 years. Descriptive statistics were used in the paper to give the data a pictorial outlook.

HISTORY OF WITCH HUNTING IN INDIA

“Put the DAYAN on fire”; “Kill the DAINI”; “She is a WITCH”

These are few sentences used in India till date.

Dayan or Daini, who are they?

Witch hunting is an occurrence in many parts of India. The highest incidences have been reported from different states in India such as Rajasthan, Gujarat, Assam, West Bengal, Bihar, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Orissa.

People from different regions use different names, for instance, dakan, dayan, banamati, chetabadi, chillangi, hawa or evil eye, dahani, tonhi, etc. The names may be different but the practice seems to take a more or less similar form; witch hunts remain a persistent scourge in rural parts of India. [Mahim Pratap Singh, 2013]

The term “witch” is used in the context to identify a “woman”, who is alleged to be involved in black magic and causing harm to others. The society terms such women as witch. She is considered to be an ill woman for the society, in which she lives in. Normally, such women do not have living relatives. She manages to outlive her children and grandchildren, who might have succumbed to an epidemic of some sort. Society, cannot accept the fact that women can survive such a calamity unless she possess some strange powers.

The term dayan can be itself found in the ancient Hindu scriptures and the dayan cult emerged not until during the fifteenth century in Maharashtra. With the advent of the British rulers in India, many western thoughts and beliefs got infused into the traditional thoughts and belief system of the people in different parts. During the 1840s and 1850s, Rajputana (present day Rajasthan) and Jharkhand’s Chotta Nagpur region were the breeding grounds for witch-hunts. At the same time, witch hunting were also reported in the Singhbhum and the Santhal Parganas regions. However, during the period 1930 – 1970’s, the practice scaled down in its intensity due to the Adivasi movement, but has reemerged during the eighties. Ever since then, there are no signs of abatement [Mahim Pratap Singh, 2015].

According to sources in the Central Ministry of Home Affairs, two thousand two hundred fifty-seven witch-craft murders took place in India ever since the year 2000 [Betwa Sharma, 2012]. A Human Rights Committee report puts this figure around two thousand five hundred. According to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), around two thousand four hundred cases of witch-hunting have been registered across India during the period from 1999 – 2012

[NCRB Report, 2015]. But, it needs to be remembered that the actual figures will be many times higher, because a large number of cases goes unreported. At least twenty States in India, which are the homes for the different indigenous tribal communities, the witch-hunting phenomenon predominates. Once practiced only by tribal communities, the witch-hunting phenomenon is presently observed amongst the Dalits as well as other minority communities [Travis M. Andrews and Swati Gupta, 2016]. It has been compared with infectious diseases as it is slowly spreading to newer and newer areas [Ata Mallick, 2008].

No satisfactory explanations of the preponderance of women have appeared. Although the proportions varied among regions on the whole among three fourth of accused witches are women.

Although the early modern practice of witch hunts ended several centuries ago, hundreds of women are known to have been killed in Rajasthan in recent decades based on accusations of witchcraft and the number assaulted may have been in the thousands. The point to be noted here is that such attacks are against the law. Murder of someone as a suspect witch is a crime. 23 of 29 cases involved accusations that the woman attacked had caused illness, disease or death. Scapegoating, village rivalries, inheritance conflicts and female threats to patriarchy are introduced in explanations of early modern hunts and similar theories are raised to explain attacks on witches in contemporary India. [Gaskill Malcolm, 2010]

LET THE DATA SPEAK:

INDIAN CONTEXT-

The latest report of the National Crime Report Bureau (NCRB) reports that 2290 women are hunted in India by branding them as ‘witch’, between 2001 to 2014, on alleged charges of practising witchcraft. These are the numbers that are logged in, the unrecorded ones are expected to be far more than this numbers.

Table 1: State-wise Data (NCRB)

Year	Jharkhand	Odisha	Andhra Pradesh	Madhya Pradesh	Haryana	Chattisgarh	Bihar	Rajasthan
2014	47	32	02	24	-	16	06	29
2013	54	24	15	11	-	07	-	49
2012	26	32	24	10	-	08	13	06

2011	36	39	28	15	05	17	-	100
2010	15	31	26	18	57	08	02	21
2009	37	28	27	23	30	06	02	21
2008	52	23	23	16	25	15	-	21
2007	50	28	33	14	30	08	-	14
2006	29	36	26	13	34	10	11	27
2005	26	25	75	13	28	09	01	20
2004	26	22	24	14	-	11	-	14
2003	19	26	37	26	-	09	-	23
2002	26	39	23	24	-	04	01	34
2001	21	30	20	13	-	14	01	27
Total	464	415	383	234	209	142	37	406

Table 2: Witch Hunting Incidences in Rajasthan (Year 2001-14)

Journal for Multidisciplinary Studies
International Peer Review Multidisciplinary Journal

In several districts across Rajasthan, e.g. Banswara, Bhilwara, Chittorgarh, Dungarpur, Kota, Sawai Madhopur, Tank and Udaipur, witch-hunting is prevalent. Most of the victims do not even lodge complaints with the police fearing retaliation, and hence continue to live amidst fear, desperation and stigma for the rest of their lives. In Rajasthan, as many as one hundred thirty seven women were killed in witch-hunting cases during 2004 – 2009. The State Government indeed took up the matter seriously and due to non-existence of a law, the State Home Department issued a circular in 2004 for speedy action in matters of atrocities against women, particularly in witch-hunting and witch-labelling cases. It has directed higher officers to routinely review the investigation of such cases [Archana Mishra, 2003]. The percentage of women who were dependent on agriculture and animal husbandry declined from 55.6% to 41.3% in a study, after they were labelled as witches by the community. The reason is either the community grabbed their land or they were not being allowed to cultivate in their fields anymore. The branded women are subjected to various forms of torture, including immolation, branding with hot iron rods, hurting of genitals, rape or even forcing to commit suicide [Dhuraba Hazarika, 2018]. The State finally passed The Rajasthan Prevention of Witch-Hunting Act, 2015 in April 2015. The number of incidences in Rajasthan is comparatively low, as per NCRB statistics of 2008 – 2013. According to NCRB figures, the total number of witchcraft incidents in Rajasthan is three hundred ninety six for the period 1999 – 2014. [NCRB Report, 2015]

CAUSES OF WITCH HUNTING: SOCIOLOGICAL OVERVIEW

Witch hunting is one of the most dangerous superstitions prevailing all over India. Meanwhile in the last fifteen years, Rajasthan witnessed more than 400 cases of witch hunting. The witch is called as 'dayan' in local dialect and is believed to cause ailment to people, destroy crops and other livestock etc. She is usually identified by an 'ojha', 'bez' or 'bhopas' (all names for witch doctors) and either banished from the community or killed.

Various studies are undertaken to understand the practice of witch hunting worldwide and they attribute it to different reasons beyond mere superstition.

More interestingly, the instigator(s) of the violence are generally related to the victim through kinship, community or neighborhood ties. A most significant finding of the previous studies is that a very large segment of the perpetrators are related to the victims through ties of marriage. Moreover, the two seem to belong to comparable social and economic strata.

Although allegations about use of “supernatural” powers are invariably present in cases of witch-hunting—land, property, jealousy, sexual advances and other common sources of tension between social intimates were found in a large number of cases. Counter narratives in every case make for a more complex understanding of witch hunting than what the framework of “superstition” suggests. As the instigators are persons who are proximate to the victim, the plausibility of conflicts, tensions and jealousies between them is reinforced. While the ojha (a shaman or an oracle) appears in majority (not all) of the cases, the tensions and conflicts in many cases exist prior to the entry of the ojha, suggesting that they tend to confirm rather than initiate the accusation.

The factors for hunting of witches can be studied into two dimensions viz. early period and contemporary period. In early period the superstition was the prime factor for witch hunting. During that period the people were illiterate and remain backward in all walks of social life. Also the atmosphere was not favorable to them to acquire education. They did not have medical facilities in the locality. In fact, the outbreak of disease, ailments of infant etc. were treated by the local physician. In addition to this, the rivalry among the quacks or Ojhas was a common issue which was a culminating factor for murder in the name of witch hunting. There was also casuist or false monger in the village for horrors killing of witch.

However, in contemporary period the witch hunting has a different purpose. The planned murder due to personal enmity, political rivalry, property rivalry, jealousy on prospering family etc. is covered by so called witch hunting. However, still the superstition factor plays a great role in witch hunting in remote villages of Rajasthan. [Dwimalu et.al, 2011]

The Manifest And Latent Causes:

Traditional Superstitious Belief: The belief in the practice of witch craft has a deeper connection with Rajasthan’s spiritual history. As since 3000 BC all diseases and mental disorders were treated as being caused by uncanny super naturals, some of which are supposed to dwell every nearby human habitat in the countryside.

It’s also believed that planet bestowed its devotees the art of black magic and sorcery. Various folklores describe its connection with astrology and practice of witchcraft (kaala jaadu). Similarly after centuries past in rural Rajasthan the *bhopas*, a traditional medicine man, is revered for his skills at countering black magic. According to folklore, the medicine man learns

his skills which include identifying and curing a witch (dayan), but witches are said to be born with their powers. In patriarchal communities this is a convenient distinction.

Lack of Education and Awareness: Illiteracy is one of the most effective dynamic pressures, which may have different root causes and potential to generate many unsafe conditions. Such unsafe conditions combined with some external threats mainly superstitions, which causes different problems to the rural community especially nomadic tribes and tribal community in which the practice of witch hunt is prevalent. Illiteracy also halts the overall progress of the community. So, practical education to all members of the vulnerable community including women is necessary for overall development of the community.

Poor Health Care System: Every year, many people die of malaria, diarrhoea, and jaundice etc., in the tribal people-dominated areas of Rajasthan. Due to the extreme ignorance of the administration, these people lack proper education, and is still today far from the glare of the media. As the people of this belt are unaware of the modern ways of health and hygiene, various diseases including tuberculosis, cancer, cerebral malaria, typhoid, encephalopathy, encephalitis, meningitis, metabolic encephalopathy, jaundice etc., break out easily among them without their knowledge. And which is later linked in illogical way of treatment and finally leading to witchcraft and hunt.

Poverty: Poverty and violence go hand in hand. It has been witnessed several time that drought, epidemic leads to a large increase in the murder of “witches”—typically elderly women, widow, spinsters killed by relatives—but not other murders. The findings provide novel evidence on the role of income shocks in causing violent crime, and religious violence in particular.

Victimization of Women: In Rajasthan, there is a steep growth in number of cases of witch hunting which had resulted due to clash over claim for property . In present days, branding someone as witch is becoming a tool to assert domination over other’s property, personal rivalry and to create new power centre in village. There are also instances of witch hunting being used against families who emerged as powerful, challenging the existing power structure of the village. Further, there are instances, where women are accused of witch after they deny sex with man. Many young widows and unmarried women goes through this problem, when the man they have rejected accuse them of being witch and spread rumors among the villagers to hunting the witches.

MEASURES TAKEN BY GOVERNMENT OF RAJASTHAN

The social justice and empowerment department has directed district collectors to strictly enforce the Prevention of Witch-Hunting Act of 2015 in their districts. The department has also drafted a multipronged strategy to fight this menace. It has asked collectors to identify the pockets in their districts where the practice of witchcraft is still prevalent and launch special campaigns against the social evil and initiate schemes for the rehabilitation of victims.

Additional chief secretary, social justice and empowerment, J C Mohanty said a model frame work was being formulated to tackle this menace which is still in vogue at least in some pockets of the state. "The district collectors and district superintendents of police have been directed to identify the 'tantriks' and keep a watch on their activities. Local police stations also have to make a list of such people by December this year," he said.

The department has identified 14 most sensitive districts where the practice of witchcraft is still prevalent. They are Jaipur, Bundi, Tonk, Chittorgarh, Bhilwara, Rajsamand, Udaipur, Ajmer, Jhalawar, Kota, Pratapgarh, Banswara, Sawai Madhopur and Dungarpur. [TOI, 2015-11-07]

The department has also decided to launch campaign at the grassroots level against the inhuman practice of witch hunting in collaboration with NGOs, Community Liaison Group (CLGs), Adult Literacy Program, Women Self Help Groups (SHGs), and peoples' representatives.

Another important aspect is rehabilitation of the victims and providing them support systems. The allotment of housing plot, medical care, water, electricity, pension etc., will be provided to them under the existing scheme.

Why The Laws Failed To Curb The Practice of Witch Hunting in Rajasthan?

Are we really do not know the reasons?

Lack of awareness and our limited efforts is the answer. In society, the evil practices are carried out because no one bothers to raise voice against it. We, the residents and governmental officers, do not take proper steps to curb the violence against women in the name of witch hunting. Most of the Police officers do not lodge complaints or take immediate actions against the evil practice. Peoples still believe in existence of witches and the power of witch craft due lack of awareness and education. In villages, peoples believe, and feel an urge to kill the witches to save their lives. Superstitious beliefs and old traditional practices are root causes which gave birth to the evil child -witchcraft.

CONCLUSION

Witch hunting or witch branding is such a phenomenon which ruin the person's reputation, property, family and life. It is very surprising that in 21st century, when we talk about women empowerment in all walks of life, the practices like witch hunting still exists. It is also surprising to see that, this practice is also prevalent among educated people; the case of the national athlete Debojani Bora further proves that being national level athlete would neither save one from being victim of witch branding. The practices of witch-hunting or witch branding are increasing day by day as per the report of various NGO and social activists. In the present days, this practice has lead to other directions, such as gaining property, and to take personal or political revenge. There are several reasons for with hunting or witch branding. However, most prominent and dangerous issue is traditional belief, which is attached to it. People are reluctant to easily give up their traditional belief system. This phenomenon is not only limited to Rajasthan, but it is prevalent across the country. Such a heinous crime exists due to lack of proper laws and poor execution of existing laws.. The existing laws have failed to tackle the issue, and this is evident from the increasing numbers of cases of witch hunting and witch branding. This social menace is different from other similar offences. Therefore, special laws are required to cure this social menace. It must also be mentioned that NGOs, social activists play a vital role in curbing this menace in absence of special law. However, this author argues that it is not only the legal provisions which must be brought in or properly implemented, but all stakeholders including the State commission for women, Rural health department, education department and social work department must join hands to, to tackle the issue of witch hunting. Since it is the question of deep rooted traditional belief in the people of Rajasthan as well as other places in India, it is necessary that the State and central government must take note of the issue and mobilize sensitizing pf people in this regard and bring reform in the society.

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